

ASSIMILATION TENDENCIES OF ENGLISH WORDS IN UZBEK

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Salimova Nilufar Aminjon qizi

MA student of Uzbekistan State World
Languages University, Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Tursunova Gulchekhra Norboboyevna

Senior teacher of Uzbekistan State World
Languages University, Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Abstract: *This paper presents how the Uzbek language is borrowing and assimilating the words from English. This is analysed carefully and given examples which shows specific features of assimilation of English borrowings into Uzbek.*

Key words: *International words, vocabulary, assimilation, function, borrowings, neologisms, synonyms, affixation, word formation.*

Introduction. Globalization and the expansion of mass media, particularly the Internet, have resulted in a significant increase in international vocabulary. All languages are influenced by the cultural and social environment in which they operate, and varied cross-national exchanges are reflected in vocabulary. International terms play a significant role in a variety of terminological systems, including science, industry, and art vocabulary. This vocabulary's etymological sources illustrate the evolution of world civilization.

In linguistics, an internationalism or international term is a loanword that has the same or comparable meaning and etymology in numerous languages that can be translingually. As a result of simultaneous or sequential borrowings from the ultimate source, these terms appear in "many different languages"¹² (I.V.Arnold). International words are largely derived from Latin or Greek, but they can also be found in other languages. English is considered the most widely used language in the world, a rising number of internationalisms are derived from it. So, the Uzbek language is also borrowing English words in its wordstock. However, English and Uzbek are distinctive languages because of their unrelated language families. The objective of the study is to investigate what changes English borrowings undergo in Uzbek and how adaptation process occurred to its peculiarities.

Methods

In this work method of comparative typological analysis is used.

Literature review

Throughout the history there were so many arguments about how to indentify the extent of international words in different languages. This phenomenon becomes more and more widely discussed in Modern Linguistics due to the globalization process and the role of language in this process¹³. Suzanne Kemmer, a linguist, claims that the statement ""A

¹² <https://www.studymode.com/essays/Borrowings-English-Language-And-Word-271510.html>

¹³ Crystal D. English as a global language. Cambridge, 1997 - p.7

foreign word" is defined as follows in English: "When the majority of speakers do not recognize the word and believe it comes from another language, the word is referred to as a foreign word. Furthermore, the languages necessary may differ depending on the target language in question. English has provided a significant number of words to other languages, such as the sports phrases football, baseball, cricket, and golf. Borrowed words have been called "philological milestones" because they "enable us to fix appreciatively the dates of linguistic developments," according to O. Jespersen. They show us the evolution of civilization and provide us with country information». Shuchard, a well-known linguist, once observed, "No language is totally pure," implying that all languages are mingled. Borrowed words enter the language as a result of two types of influences: linguistic and extralinguistic.¹⁴

Professor A.I. Smirnitkiy addresses the main topics of etymology and borrowed words in relation to the English language in a comprehensive and consistent manner. His methodological approach to word theory is reflected in his use of the word "sameness."

We will focus our attention on the assimilation of borrowed words as a means of connection with the language system as a whole in this section. The term assimilation of a borrowed word refers to a partial or complete conformity to the recipient language's phonological, graphical, and morphological criteria, as well as its semantic system.

Linguists distinguish phonetic, grammatical, and lexical assimilation of borrowings since the process encompasses changes in sound-form, morphological structure, grammar features, meaning, and usage.

For many years, English has maintained its status as a global lingua franca, and the causes stated above have played a significant influence in the development of various variants of the language. English, British English, American English, and Australian English are only a few examples. Canadian English, Indian English, Philippine English, and a variety of other languages are among them. They may differ, when it comes to grammar (Past Simple is used instead of Present Perfect in American English), They speak dinkumin Australia when they mean "true"), phonological I sound is important), and vocabulary (they say dinkumin Australia when they mean "true"). In Canada, the pronunciation is [bi:n] (as opposed to [bin] in British English). Since English has or has had a direct impact on those countries, these types have emerged and are still spoken as a dialect. Countries that do not give the language any official status, on the other hand, learn English as a foreign language. According to the Open University, around 700 million people worldwide speak English as a second language. Uzbekistan is one of the countries that considers and studies it as a foreign language. Despite the fact that Uzbeks do not use English as freely and fluently as Indians, we may see them being utilized when discussing Internet, telecommunication, food, computers, and other topics in the news. However, due to a lack of direct interaction with the English language, the words are frequently mispronounced. For example, Paynet, a service that deposits money into people's phone accounts, is spelled incorrectly as Paynet. Many people say [painet], however the correct term is [peinet]. It is so commonly used that it has become a verb. It is generally recognized by the public, according to EFL. Nonetheless, [ko:l mi] is the

¹⁴ <https://cyberpedia.su/23xa525.html>

correct pronunciation of the word combination Call me message. This is due to people's misconception that in English, a letter is pronounced as [ei] in all words because everyone knows Basic English words like apple and cat from school. As a result, people try to pronounce the 'a' sound the way they were taught during their classes. How Uzbek words are pronounced that is usually rather obvious in the the elderly's speech in a certain extent. As more young people become aware of such words and interpretations, correct pronunciation is becoming more common. The effect of Uzbek pronunciation on the food name KFC can be seen. Instead of separating letters, they say [kepsi]. It's caused by a change in consonants: The letter [f] is pronounced as in most circumstances (falokat – palakat), [p] is used. Imo [imo], BMW [bi emve], and others are instances. [yumees] UMS. [aimo], [bi em] are the proper Standard English pronunciations of those words. [juemes] and [double ju]. Although the term Uzlish has not yet been coined and is not yet included in the dictionary, any researchers involved in English learning and teaching, as well as internationally popular dictionaries. It's commonly used to refer to the English-based Uzbek variation. The English words, on the other hand are currently limited to brand names and words of technological improvement.

English borrowings in Uzbek include words like "student," "master," "city," "house", and "river," which have become part of words used at least once a day in our country. Also, loan terms like as «Kolxoz», «sputnik», «demokratiya», «efir», and others are immediately identifiable. However, ordinary people do not regard words like «maktab», «kitob», «muhahhat», «ilm», «badavlat», and others as loan words because they are deeply embedded in native lexicon and are regularly used by people. Actually, these words were taken from Arabic and Persian languages, according to the etymology of these words.

During XIX century, new notions began to come into Uzbek language from Russian and via Russian from European languages. They denote new notions, new inventions which don't have equivalence in Uzbek that's why they are completely assimilated borrowings: стол, стул, ручка, паровоз, студент, министр, операция, (Latin) грамматика, комедия, театр, музей, опера, (Greek) солдат, галстук, штаб, лагерь, (German) костюм, пальто кабинет, генерал, (French) опера, ария, ложа, топор, (Italian) трамвай, вокзал, митинг, футбол, баскетбол, бокс (English).

In the sphere of sport, we discover several English words such as football, match, tennis. A wide number of English words related to clothing can be found in the vocabulary: pullover, sweater, nylon, breed, and so on. Many worldwide English words have their origins in cinema and other types of entertainment: film, club, cocktail Jazz, and so on. Balalaika, Bolshevik, cosmonaut, czar, Kremlin rouble mammoth, sambo, steppe, vodka are just a few of the Russian phrases that have been taken into English and many other languages, making them universal.

To conclude, the assimilation of loan words in the manner of their connection with the linguistic system as a whole must be prioritized. The term assimilation of a borrowed word refers to a partial or complete conformity to the receiving language's phonological, graphical, and morphological criteria, as well as its semantic system. The degree of assimilation is determined by the length of time and frequency with which the word has been used in the receiving language. Oral borrowings resulting from personal connections

are assimilated more thoroughly and quickly than literary borrowings, i.e. borrowings resulting from written speech.

The following subject groups of English and other borrowings in Uzbek language are identified by the research: financial and economic vocabulary, e.g. broke, defolt, audit, barter, voucher, passkard, treyder, tender, overtaym and etc; vocabulary related to the organization of business, trade and production. e.g marketing, menejment, monitoring, sponsor, holding, advayzer, server, and etc.; socio-political vocabulary, e.g. globalizatsiya, impichment, imidj, sammit, elit-klub and etc.; vocabulary related to the organization of shows, telecasts, competitions, advertisements, and etc.. e.g. shou-biznes, video klip, disk, imidj-meyker, klipmeyker and etc.: sport vocabulary, e.g. bodibilding, vindso'rfing, skuter, boksing, and etc.: vocabulary related to the education, science, IT and computing e.g. laptop, noutbuk, kompyuter, antivirus, mobil telefon, aplikatsion forma, and etc.; vocabulary related to cuisine, e.g. fast-fud, gamburger, chizburger, xot-dog, sushi, spaghetti, pankeyk, and others: vocabulary related to International organizations e.g. UNICEF, UNN, DVV, British Council, NATO, ADB and many others; vocabulary related to cosmetology, e.g. piling, spot, jakuzi, manikyur, pedikyur, spa, vaytining and etc.; vocabulary related to animals, e.g. leopard, pantera, koala, jirafa, zebra, anaconda, and etc., and finally, clothes and textile vocabulary, e.g. pijama, jinsi, shorti, tunika, kapri and etc.

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